

CONDENSATIONS OF ARYL DIAZONIUM SALTS WITH REACTIVE
UNSATURATED COMPOUNDS. PART II. ACTION
OF ARYL DIAZONIUM CHLORIDES
WITH MALEIC ACID

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Aryl diazonium chlorides containing a negative substituent can react with maleic acid in the presence of copper chloride and sodium acetate to give β -aryl acrylic acids. Contrary to expectation, the use of acetone as a solvent is found to be unnecessary in these reactions. The latter affords a method for the synthesis of certain negatively substituted cinnamic acids directly.

Dhingra and Mathur (*J Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 24, 123) extended the reactions of aryl diazonium chlorides with unsaturated carbonyl compounds (cf. Meerwein, Buchner and Emster, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1939, ii, 152, 237; Koelsch, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 65, 57; Koelsch and Boekelheide, *ibid*, 1944, 66, 412) to an unsymmetrical compound containing two activating groups e.g., citraconic acid, and found that β -arylation occurred, the product in every case being α -methylcinnamic acids formed thus,

This mode of aryl coupling lends support to the free radical mechanism advanced for such reactions by Koelsch *et al.* (*loc. cit.*). In the light of the above reactions it will be of interest to ascertain if cinnamic acids could be synthesised by using maleic acid. With this object in view a systematic study has been made of the reactions of aryl diazonium chlorides with maleic acid.

The presence of acetone and cupric chloride (0.005*M*), and the maintenance of a proper p_{H} are recognised as favourable conditions for successful coupling (cf. Meerwein *et al.*, *loc. cit.*, Koelsch *et al.*, *loc. cit.*). In fact, acetone is said to have a specific effect on the reactions. *p*-Nitrobenzene diazonium chloride and β -naphthalene diazonium chloride, when reacted with maleic acid under these conditions (vide experimental), afford the expected β -aryl acrylic acids, but in poor yield.

When, however, the above coupling reactions are repeated without acetone, the yields of the acids in (2) and (3) are improved considerably. Similar results are obtained with *o*-, and *m*-nitrobenzene diazonium chlorides. These experiments and others (*vide infra*) clearly demonstrate that the use of acetone is not essential in these reactions, rather its presence lowers the yield of the desired acids, presumably due to the formation of chloroacetone by a side reaction (*cf. Meerwein, loc. cit.*).

That these coupling reactions run the course as indicated in equations (2) and (3) is shown by the liberation of carbon dioxide, by the properties of the acids, and in most cases by the determination of their equivalent weights. In the case of the nitro-acids, comparison with authentic preparations of *o*-, *m*-, and *p*-nitrocinnamic acids by Perkin's reaction affords further confirmation as to the nature of these products.

Maintaining the usual conditions as regards the catalyst and the *pH*, but omitting acetone, it is thus seen that representative class of mono- and di-negatively substituted amines can undergo the coupling reactions after diazotisation. The cinnamic acids obtained demand little further purification and in most cases they have been obtained in workable amounts. A practical advantage that accrues by this modification lies in conducting these reactions in aqueous solutions and even in solutions more dilute than usual cases. On these accounts, and due to ready availability of maleic acid, these syntheses are useful for the preparation of cinnamic acids.

The yields of the acids are adversely affected if the amount of sodium acetate used is less or more than the equivalent of available hydrochloric acid or it is replaced by pyridine. The poor yields are also obtained if the temperature is below 20° and excessive amounts of haloid ions are present in the reaction mixture.

The yield of *o*-nitrocinnamic acid, obtained as above, appears to be strikingly poor when compared with the yields of other cinnamic acids. The low yield cannot be ascribed to steric hindrance of the nitro group in the *ortho* position in the *o*-nitrobenzene diazonium chloride, as the yields of the halogen acids from *o*-chloro-, *o*-bromo- and *o*-iodo-benzene diazonium chlorides do not fall off progressively from the chloro to the iodo compound, i.e., even when the bulkiest iodine group is reached. Reactions with 2 : 6-dichloro-, and 2 : 4-dinitrobenzene diazonium chlorides suggest that the presence of an additional negative group in mono-negatively substituted diazonium chloride does not augment the yield of the cinnamic acid. In all such cases, where poor yields are obtained, more of the tarry matter is found to be present in the reaction mixture. The low yields are likely due to the highly negative nature of the parent amines, which in *pH* range of 3 to 5 give easily decomposable *syn*-diazo forms and at higher *pH* pass over to the inactive *anti*-diazotate (*cf. Saunders, "The Aromatic Diazo Compounds and their Technical Applications", Edward Arnold Co., London, 1936, pp. 72-73.*

Aniline and those amines, which contain a positive substituent in the nucleus, are found to give diazonium chlorides which resist all attempts to coupling with maleic acid either in the presence or absence of acetone. Such amines are, however, known to react with unsaturated aliphatic esters or nitriles (Koelsch, *loc. cit.*), though in poor yield. Attempts to condense benzene diazonium chloride as its mercury chloride double compound met with partial success, yielding only 6% of the cinnamic acid.

EXPERIMENTAL

3-Nitro-4-methylaniline, *m*-chloro-, *m*-bromo- and *o*-bromoanilines were prepared in the laboratory. The rest of the amines and the maleic acid were from stock and were of requisite chemical purity.

For the determination of the equivalent weight of the acids, the sample (0.1-0.2 g.) was first dissolved in a known excess (10 c. c.) of *N*/5-caustic soda solution. Subsequently the alkali was neutralised by adding just 10 c.c. of *N*/5-sulphuric acid. In this way the acid was reprecipitated in a very fine hydrated form which could be titrated better than the crystalline sample taken in alcohol, with alkali (*N*/25) to the pink colour with phenolphthalein as indicator. The method was checked with an authentic sample of *p*-nitrocinnamic acid.

The *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitrocinnamic acids were synthesised for comparison by heating the corresponding nitrobenzaldehydes (1.1 g. each) with powdered anhydrous sodium acetate (0.5 g.) and acetic anhydride (3 c.c.) at 180° for 8 hours.

Condensations of p-Nitrobenzene and β-Naphthalene Diazonium Chlorides with Maleic Acid, Copper Chloride and Sodium Acetate, with and without Acetone.—*p*-Nitroaniline (0.025*M*, 3.45 g.) was dissolved by warming in hydrochloric acid (conc., 6 c.c., 2.5 times the base) diluted with water (9-12 c.c.). The solution was slightly cooled and the base hydrochloride precipitated by the addition of crushed ice (3-4 g.) and accompanied by external cooling with ice. To it was added an ice-cold solution of sodium nitrite (2.5 g., 68% pure) in water (7 c.c.) all at once, and the mixture thoroughly stirred for 10 minutes. In this way practically the whole of the amine was diazotised. The diazo solution was filtered and added to a solution containing maleic acid (0.025*M*, 2.9 g.), acetone (10 c. c.), copper chloride (1 g.) in water and sodium acetate (5.75 g.) in water (10 c. c.). The mixture was stirred throughout and the temperature was maintained at 30-40°. There was brisk effervescence for nearly one hour and it continued slowly for another 2 to 3 hours when a brownish solid deposited. The supernatant liquid was decanted off and the residue washed with a little water. It was then extracted with warm 5% aqueous sodium bicarbonate. The extract was acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid. An acid was precipitated (0.2 g.) which, after trituration with benzene, was crystallised from ethyl alcohol in needles, m.p. 282-84° (mixed m.p. with an authentic sample of *p*-nitrocinnamic acid). It decolorised 1% aqueous potassium permanganate and bromine water in the cold.

A similar experiment with β -naphthalene diazonium chloride gave only a trace of an unsaturated acid.

The experiment with *p*-nitrobenzene diazonium chloride with 1/50th the quantities in a Lunge's nitrometer, filled with mercury, showed small amount of carbon dioxide in the gas phase, indicating side reactions. The volume of nitrogen (11.6 c. c. at N. T. P.), however, corresponded with the amount of the diazonium chloride used.

When the condensations with *p*-nitro-, and β -naphthalene diazonium chlorides with maleic acid were repeated without using acetone, but keeping the bulk with water to 40 c. c., the yields of the unsaturated acids were as follows :--

	Amount	M. p.
<i>p</i> -Nitro derivative	2.5 g.	282-89°
β -Naphthalene	0.4	192-94°

Condensations of various Aryl Diazonium Chlorides with Maleic Acid in the presence of Copper Chloride and Sodium Acetate, but without Acetone

The amines (0.025 *M*) were diazotised in the same manner as with the nitroaniline and the filtered solutions (20 c. c.) were added to maleic acid (0.025 *M*) in the presence of copper chloride (1 g.) and sodium acetate (5.75 g.). The total volume of the reaction mixture was adjusted with water to 45 c. c. The temperature was maintained within 30 to 40°. The effervescence was more or less vigorous for $\frac{1}{2}$ to $\frac{3}{4}$ hour and then continued for another 2 to 3 hours. From the reaction products, the acids were extracted out with warm aqueous sodium bicarbonate, leaving behind the neutral matter, tar etc. More tar was present in experiments with *o*-nitro-, 2 : 6-dichloro- and 2 : 4-dinitro-benzene diazonium chlorides. From the extracts, the unsaturated acids were precipitated out in sufficiently pure conditions after acidification. The acids could be recrystallised from alcohol or dilute alcohol. Trituration of the precipitated acid with benzene was only resorted to in the case of the nitro-acid.

In the diazotisation of the naphthylamines, considerable insoluble undiazotised matter was left behind. 2 : 4-Dinitrobenzene diazonium chloride was obtained indirectly. 2 : 4-Dinitroaniline (*M*/80, 2.38 g.) was diazotised (cf. Groggins, "Unit Processes in Organic Synthesis", Mc Graw-Hill Book Company, Inc., London, 1938, p. 194) by nitrosylsulphuric acid with sodium nitrite (1.25 g.) and sulphuric acid (conc., 6 c. c.). The filtered diazonium sulphate was treated with a paste made of barium chloride (32 g.). There was a lowering in temperature accompanied by evolution of hydrogen chloride. The mixture was filtered from the precipitated barium sulphate. Sodium acetate (33 g.) was then added, as in other cases, equivalent to the available hydrogen chloride.

The results with the various diazotised amines, including those of the *p*-nitro and β -naphthalene derivatives (*vide supra*) are summarised in Table I,

below. The mixed melting points recorded are those of the acids from the diazotised nitroanilines, admixed with an authentic sample of the expected nitrocinnamic acid (vide p. 386). Where there are mentioned more than one melting point in literature, only that which corresponds to the experimental value has been cited.

TABLE I

Amine (diazotised) & wt.	Amount of acid.	Yield.	M.p. of the pure acids.		Ar.CH : CH.CO ₂ H equiv.		Re- mark.
			Found.	Lit.	Found.	Calc.	
<i>p</i> -Nitroaniline (3.45 g.)	2.8 g.	59%	282-84 ¹	285° (Alway & Bonner, <i>Amer. Chem. J.</i> , 1904, 32, 392)	195	193	Mixed m. p. 263-85°.
β -Naphthylamine (3.60 g.)	0.4	8	192-94°	196° (Roussset, <i>Bull. soc. chim.</i> , 1897, 17, 815.)	201	198	...
<i>m</i> -Nitroaniline (3.45 g.)	1.2	24	196-96°	198° (Schiff, <i>Ber.</i> , 1878, 11, 1782)	198	193	Mixed m.p. 196-96°
<i>o</i> -Nitroaniline (3.45 g.)	0.35	7.3	210-37°	239-40° (Gabriel & Meyer, <i>Ber.</i> , 1881, 14, 830)	197	193	Mixed m.p. 238-40°
<i>p</i> -Chloroaniline (3.2 g.)	1.3	28.5	240-41°	240-42° (Gabriel & Herz- berg, <i>Ber.</i> , 1883, 16, 2039)	187	182.5	...
<i>p</i> -Bromoaniline (4.3 g.)	1.82	28.8	*248-51°	Sinters at 248° and m.p. 251-53° (Gabriel, <i>Ber.</i> , 1882, 15, 2301)	232	227	...
<i>m</i> -Chloroaniline (3.2 g.)	1.30	28.5	*174-75°	176° (Gabriel & Herzberg, <i>Ber.</i> , 1883, 16, 2036)	186	182.5	...
<i>m</i> -Bromoaniline (4.3 g.)	1.5	28.5	176-77°	176-77° (Miller & Rohde, <i>Ber.</i> , 1890, 23, 1890)	234	227	...
<i>o</i> -Chloroaniline (3.2 g.)	1.26	27.5	198-99°	198-99° (Gabriel & Herz- berg, <i>Ber.</i> , 1883, 16, 2036)	190	182.5	...
<i>o</i> -Bromoaniline (4.3 g.)	1.3	23.2	211-12°	212-12.5° (Gabriel, <i>Ber.</i> , 1882, 15, 2295)	234	227	...
<i>o</i> -Iodoaniline (2.7 g.)	0.8	28.3	212-13°	212-14° (Gabriel & Herzberg, <i>Ber.</i> , 1883, 16, 2037)	...	...	With M/80 amount
4-Methyl-3-nitro- aniline (3.6 g.)	0.7	13.5	170-71°	170-71° (Hanzlik, <i>Ber.</i> , 1899, 32, 2286)	212	207	...
2 : 6-Dichloro- aniline (4.0 g.)	1.1	20.8	182-83°	184° (Reich, <i>Bull. soc. chim.</i> , 1917, iv, 21, 218-221)	220	217	...
2 : 4-Dinitro- aniline (2.3 g.)	0.45	7.3	176-78°	179° (Friedlander, <i>Monatsh.</i> , 1881, 23, 635)	...	...	With M/80 amount
α -Naphthylamine (3.2 g.)	0.95	7.0	205-07°	205° (Roussset, <i>Bull. soc. chim.</i> , 1897, iii, 17, 813).	...	...	...

* From dilute alcohol.

Experiments repeated with *m*-, and *p*-nitrobenzene diazonium chlorides and β -naphthalene diazonium chloride in a total bulk of 120 c. c. gave identical results. Similarly variation in the amount of copper chloride (0.5 to 6 g.) had little effect on the yields. The yields were adversely affected when in experiments e.g. with *o*-, *m*-, and *p*-nitrobenzene diazonium chlorides, 3 g. or 10g. of sodium acetate were used. Similarly the use of pyridine (5 c. c.) in place of sodium acetate e.g. in experiments with *p*-nitro-, *p*-chloro-, *p*-bromo-, *m*-nitro-, *m*-chloro- benzene diazonium chlorides and β -naphthalene diazonium chloride, gave lower yields of the acids. In the experiment with the *o*-chlorobenzene diazonium chloride the use of potassium chloride (7.45 g.), potassium bromide (11.9 g.) or potassium iodide (16.6 g.) in amounts four times (*M*/10) the equivalent of the base, lessened the yields of the acid but increased the amount of the neutral product. No acid was obtained from diazotised aniline, *o*-xylidine, *o*- and *p*-anisidines, *p*-aminoacetanilide with or without acetone. The compound, probably $C_6H_5 \cdot N_2 \cdot Cl \cdot HgCl_2 \cdot H_2O$, (*M*/40, 10 g.), prepared in the way of the antimony compound (cf. May, *J Chem. Soc.*, 1912, 101, 1037) when heated at 120° with maleic acid (*M*/40, 2.9 g.) in glacial acetic acid (15 c. c.) gave in the presence of copper chloride (1 g.) and sodium acetate (5.75 g.) only 0.2 g. of cinnamic acid (i.e., 6% of the theory).

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Received March 19, 1947.